

Six upland rice varieties released in Nigeria

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Six upland rice varieties, FARO 38 to FARO 43, have been released for cultivation in Nigeria. They were best in the 1984-86 multilocational Coordinated Rice Evaluation Trials (see table).

Short-duration FARO 38 and 39 have been recommended for dry upland environments. They are high yielding and resistant to diseases and drought. Their grains are clean and short bold. FARO 39 combines medium height and better plant type. Its cooking quality is also good. Both these varieties outyielded short-duration check ITA257 by 28%.

FARO 40, 41, 42, and 43 are medium-duration varieties

recommended for moist environments. FARO 40, a composite developed at NCRI, is resistant to lodging and diseases. It possesses better cooking quality than the commonly cultivated variety FARO 11. FARO 41 was the highest yielder (32% over check) among the medium-duration entries. It possesses better plant type and good cooking quality. FARO 42 and 43 are shorter than FARO 11 and are resistant to lodging. □

Performance of 6 newly released upland varieties in multilocation trials. Nigeria, 1984-86.

Variety	Former name	Ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Panicles (no./m ²)	Av grain yield		Grain type ^a	Amylose content (%)	Reaction ^b to	
					t/ha	% over check			Blast	Rice yellow mottle virus
<i>Short-duration</i>										
FARO 38	IRAT133	87	72	206	3.2	28	SB	15.0	R	MR
FARO 39	IRAT144	103	76	198	3.2	28	SB	24.0	R	R
ITA257 (check)	—	88	68	185	2.5	—	MB	14.0	R	R
<i>Medium-duration</i>										
FARO 40	FAROX299	118	96	167	2.2	0	MB	22.0	R	R
FARO 41	IRAT170	100	97	177	2.9	32	MB	22.5	MR	R
FARO 42	ART12	105	96	172	2.8	27	MB	16.8	MR	MR
FARO 43	ITA128	108	97	178	2.3	4	MB	20.8	MR	R
FARO 11 (check)	—	123	97	179	2.2	—	MB	19.2	MR	R

^aSB = short bold, MB = medium bold. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

Performance of short-duration rice varieties

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Short-duration, high-yielding rice varieties were compared with Dangi variety in three farmers' fields and at the SciTech Centre farm during the 1985

and 1986 main crop seasons. Test plots were in a completely randomized block design replicated four times.

Seeds were sown on a raised bed in Jun and transplanted at 21 d, at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 32.4-m² plots. Fertilizer (100-50 kg NPK/ha) was applied to all plots and normal management practices were followed.

Yields of K184, K23, Ratna, and IR36 were similarly and significantly

higher than those of Dangi and K35-3 (see table). Ratna and R24 produced significantly longer panicles, suggesting high yield potential.

Ratna, R24, and K184 are normally preferred by local farmers because of their resistance to lodging and substantially higher grain and straw yields compared to Dangi. IR36 has higher yields, but its straw yield is lower. □

Comparison of 6 short-duration varieties with Dangi (local) variety. Dahanu, Maharashtra, India, 1985-86.

Variety	Duration (d)	Origin	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)		Tillers (no./hill)		Panicles (no./hill)		Average panicle length (cm)	
			1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986	1985	1986
K184	100-110	Karjat (India)	4.1	4.3	1.9	3.2	12.2	13.8	11.7	12.0	19.1	17.6
K23	120-130	Karjat (India)	4.4	3.8	3.8	5.2	8.6	11.4	8.1	9.9	18.0	19.4
Ratna	110-120	KKV Dapoli (India)	4.3	3.8	2.5	5.0	10.1	12.8	9.6	11.4	21.6	20.2
IR36	100-110	IRRI	4.1	3.9	2.4	4.4	10.7	13.6	10.2	11.4	20.2	17.9
R24	120-130	Ratnagiri (India)	4.5	2.8	2.1	4.5	9.4	12.2	8.8	10.9	21.8	19.1
Dangi	110-120	Thane (India)	3.6	3.2	3.0	6.1	10.0	9.8	8.7	8.4	19.3	18.4
K35-3	80-90	Karjat (India)	2.7	3.9	1.7	5.5	10.8	12.4	10.2	11.3	18.9	18.8
Mean	—	—	4.0	3.6	2.5	4.8	10.2	12.3	9.6	10.8	19.8	18.8
CD (0.05)	—	—	0.4	0.8	1.2	1.2	ns	ns	1.7	ns	1.3	ns
(0.01)	—	—	0.5	1.2	2.0	1.9	ns	ns	2.6	ns	2.0	ns